

IMPROVING THE INSTITUTION OF ENVIRONMENTAL RESPONSIBILITY OF AGRICULTURAL PRODUCERS IN UZBEKISTAN

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ABSTRACT

The agricultural sector of the Republic of Uzbekistan, while serving as the backbone of the economy, remains vulnerable to ecological threats such as irrational land use, water scarcity, and soil degradation. According to the country's Constitution and Land Code, land is considered a national asset, and the rational use and state protection of land are strictly required. However, the dominance of traditional agricultural practices and the failure to comply with environmental standards have led to the depletion of natural resources

Introduction. The agricultural sector of the Republic of Uzbekistan, while serving as the backbone of the economy, remains vulnerable to ecological threats such as irrational land use, water scarcity, and soil degradation. According to the country's Constitution and Land Code, land is considered a national asset, and the rational use and state protection of land are strictly required. However, the dominance of traditional agricultural practices and the failure to comply with environmental standards have led to the depletion of natural resources.

Ensuring environmental sustainability and achieving the goals of the United Nations 2030 Agenda for Sustainable Development require the improvement of legal and institutional mechanisms that strengthen the responsibility of agricultural producers for the damage caused to the environment. This thesis analyzes the existing legal framework of environmental responsibility in Uzbekistan's agriculture and examines, from a legal and scientific perspective, ways to strengthen this institution through digital monitoring methods, financial incentives, and insurance mechanisms.

Uzbekistan's system of environmental responsibility is regulated by various legislative acts. The Law "On Environmental Protection" establishes the legal, economic, and organizational foundations for preserving the natural environment and the rational use of natural resources.

Environmental violations committed by agricultural producers are mainly reflected in the relevant articles of the Code of Administrative Responsibility [1]. These include:

- Misuse or negligent use of land (Article 57);
- Unauthorized deviation from land management projects (Article 68);
- Violation of water use and water consumption rules (Article 66).

In addition, liability is also established for the pollution of water bodies, air, and soil. As the most stringent measure, if agricultural products cannot be used for livestock feed or other purposes due to environmental degradation, they may be confiscated from producers and

destroyed. These norms confirm the existence of legally enforceable mechanisms for environmental protection.

The improvement of the institution of environmental responsibility should be achieved through the strengthening of legal discipline, the introduction of new financial instruments, and the implementation of digital monitoring systems.

The Agricultural Development Strategy for 2020–2030 has outlined the development and implementation of *Good Agricultural and Environmental Practices (GAEP)* to ensure the efficient use of natural resources [2]. These practices should be legally reinforced and compliance with them should become a key criterion of environmental responsibility. At the same time, the promotion of the “green” agriculture concept and the mandatory implementation of international environmental standards such as *Organic* and *Global G.A.P.* will further strengthen accountability.

In addition, the agricultural risk insurance system serves as an important financial instrument in strengthening environmental responsibility. Under the current system, if the insurer identifies cases of non-compliance with agrotechnical requirements during planting, maintenance, or harvesting, the amount of insurance coverage is reduced (for example, in cases of under-fertilization or weed infestation). Improving this mechanism — that is, directly linking the amount of insurance compensation (or liability) to the level of environmental violations and land degradation — can significantly enhance the financial accountability of producers for environmental responsibility.

Digital platforms play a decisive role in ensuring effective control over compliance with environmental standards. Improving the geographic information system of agricultural lands makes it possible to maintain a real-time database on land plots, crop conditions, and productivity. This system (for example, “*agroplatforma.uz*”) enables supervisory bodies such as “*O‘zagroinspeksiya*” to conduct remote and continuous monitoring of environmental violations (such as negligent land use or unauthorized crop placement), as well as to promptly apply measures of responsibility.

Conclusion. Improving the institution of environmental responsibility of agricultural producers in Uzbekistan is of strategic importance for the country's sustainable development. Although the existing legal norms (Administrative Code) prescribe penalties for the irrational use of land and water resources, strengthening the accountability system with institutional mechanisms is necessary to ensure its positive transformation in the future.

The main directions of improvement should include linking financial incentives to strict enforcement measures (such as reclaiming subsidies), transforming *Good Agricultural and Environmental Practices (GAEP)* into legal norms, and introducing digital monitoring systems (geoinformation platforms). In particular, linking the amount of insurance compensation within the framework of agricultural insurance to the degree of compliance with agrotechnical regulations directly connects producers' financial interests with environmental responsibility. This comprehensive approach plays a decisive role in ensuring the environmental sustainability of Uzbekistan's agricultural sector.

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